

PRACTICE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

Muydinjanov Z.R.

Teacher of the Interfaculty Department of Mathematics and Informatics of the Kokan State
Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11402846>

Abstract. *In connection with the rapid development of digital technologies, their increasing role in human life and activities, the importance of determining its nature, level, and evaluation methods is discussed, and the role of digital technologies in the development of digital competencies of future elementary school teachers is discussed.*

Keywords: *digital technology, digital competence, electronic journal, spreadsheet, electronic report, digital service, cloud technology.*

Today, the digitization of the higher education system implies the widespread introduction of digital technologies in all directions of the educational institution, and the development of digital competences of future elementary school teachers requires appropriate professional training, formation and assessment of their digital competence. The future primary class will focus on the development of digital competencies of teachers. The integration of digital technologies into the educational process is important because it is aimed at developing pedagogical methods and approaches, opening new opportunities in terms of personalization of the educational process. The development of digital competences of future elementary school teachers is considered in the modern scientific heritage as a result of the evolutionary development of their digital competences, which is declared in the teacher's professional standard as an indispensable characteristic of a teacher in modern conditions. These institutions of higher education are the basis for the development of digital competences of future elementary school teachers. The teacher should play an important role in adapting digital innovations to improve the quality of learning.

Services regularly used by the teacher to ensure the educational process and perform pedagogical activities from a personal device include: services for working with electronic educational content, electronic journal, electronic spreadsheet, accounting for the development of additional educational programs, information and communication educational platform, electronic reporting services, etc.

Because digital services, tools, and environments are so dynamic, they are constantly evolving and improving. In this regard, the constant updating and development of digital competences, the formation of the teacher's digital competence are of great importance in the convenient, effective and safe use of digital competences in pedagogical activities.

Quality of open learning materials, their fragmentation, lack of ability to integrate resources and tools from different platforms. The results of the study of digital competence allow to predict the pedagogical means of its formation.

At the same time, we consider digital competence at the same time:

the educational result of the professional training of future primary school teachers;

the result of self-development of future elementary school teachers;

the result of synthesizing the pedagogical (activity and personal) experience of future primary school teachers.

In this regard, pedagogical tools for the formation of digital competence can be presented in three thematic blocks:

1) modeling of the personal educational trajectory of future elementary school teachers during the period of studying at an educational institution, undergoing pedagogical practice, and taking advanced training courses according to higher education programs: use of e-learning resources in the educational process, as well as digital platforms for education (including ready-made high-quality e-learning content), organization of joint projects in the online environment, interaction in cloud services mystery and pedagogical communication; development of network activity and communication in social networks; use of digital tools and services in the design of various educational lesson situations, creation of electronic educational content.

This allows to form the teacher's readiness to work in modern information and communication technologies, to show possible options for working in new conditions, to encourage the use of digital technologies in the educational process, to conduct propaedeutic work on the formation of initial personal experience.

2) improving the skills of future primary school teachers on the implementation of the digitized educational process, developing methodological training in the direction of digital transformation of education using modern online educational platforms, web- a natural practice-oriented environment for the formation of digital competencies of future elementary school teachers to participate in seminars and others;

3) exchange of positive and negative pedagogical experiences within network pedagogical communities; participation in creative contests within the framework of priority national projects on digitalization of education, study of local and foreign pedagogical experience. This creates a complete picture of the advantages and disadvantages of using digital technologies in the educational process, determines the level of their effective implementation.

Thus, we can conclude that digital competence is an important professional characteristic of a teacher of higher education institutions in the environment of digital technologies. In connection with the rapid development of digital technologies and their increasing role in human life and activities, the issues of determining its nature, level, and evaluation methods are becoming urgent.

The results of the assessment of the digital competence of the future elementary school teachers presented in the study are practical in planning the modernization of the content of educational subjects related to the use of information and communication technologies in teaching, in the development of continuous education and educational programs. is important. They identify problem areas and allow to critically examine the actions of future elementary school teachers in various pedagogical situations, to evaluate the rationality of choosing and using digital tools and services to solve pedagogical problems.

Formation of digital competences of future elementary school teachers can be done in the following ways:

- Continuous self-education and professional development using Internet technologies, participation in webinars and master classes;
- provision of a methodical support system by the school;
- participation in professional skill contests, methodical development contests, improvement of science and digital competence, and identification tests;

- create a website or blog for information, future elementary school teachers and their parents, colleagues, etc.;
- development of cloud technologies, creation and use of science and elective courses or providing access to working materials through Internet services.

In our study, we considered the process of distance education as a form of using modern and popular information communication technologies to organize interactive communication in education.

An important condition for the organization of distance education is that the interacting parties have a personal computer and the global Internet, but this is not enough. In the process of distance education, it is impossible to build a dialog without interactive programs and additional software. It is precisely because of the insufficient skills of students to work with the components of the distance learning process that problems have arisen in many educational institutions.

Educational platforms not only made it possible to organize the distance education process of future elementary school teachers and make it effective, but also to improve the skills of future elementary school teachers in information and communication technologies. With the help of these resources, free webinars, video lectures and workshops were held for future elementary teachers, which helped to improve their digital competence. Thus, the development of digital competences of modern future elementary school teachers is one of the main tasks, which can be solved by continuous self-education of future elementary school teachers, professional knowledge and related to improving skills.

With the help of digital technologies, it is much easier to present teaching material to future elementary teachers, which allows for a significant extension of learning.

Multimedia resources are the most effective electronic learning resources. The convenience of this type of resource is that training information can be presented in a variety of ways: using text, graphics, photography, video, sound and animation. Based on the above, we see the need for this resource:

- uses all types of perception, all types of student's thinking and practical activities are developed accordingly. The process of providing information to students through the use of information technologies makes this process active due to the novelty of this form of work, and also makes it bright and colorful with the help of multimedia files;
- the educational process is individualized through tasks of different levels, by mastering the material in an individual form.

The advantages of information technology in education are as follows:

due to the individuality of each student, using a convenient way of perceiving information, which later forms positive educational ideas;

increase students' independence in answering questions;

improvement of one's performance due to feedback, which subsequently leads to improvement of self-control skills;

- to carry out independent research work that develops creative activity (creating construction works, modeling, making presentations).

Future elementary school teachers are recommended to use presentations to check the correctness of tasks, because a lot of time is spent on reproducing graphs and drawings, explaining tasks that lead to difficulties. In other words, electronic learning technologies imply independent learning of the material.

In this case, the teacher acts as a consultant and, if necessary, an assistant who explains unclear questions.

The main advantages of digitization are:

independence, since digital skills imply independent work, a desire for knowledge appears; future elementary school teachers will achieve great success without excessive care of the teacher;

E-learning allows you to get rid of paperwork: all textbooks are available on a computer, and a tablet can easily replace workbooks;

– economy; we are talking about office equipment, electronic gadgets and computers require replacement only in case of damage;

– simplifying the teacher's work; in e-learning, the teacher works more as an assistant, he determines the direction of movement of the future elementary school teachers. Ular raqamli ko'nikmalar orqali bilimlarni mustaqil ravishda izlay oladilar;

– a step into the future, implies rapid adaptation to the world of constantly developing technology, helps to better guide the future in the field of information technology.

In addition to the advantages of digital technologies, there are also disadvantages of the modern information education system. In this case, we must consider the risk of a negative outcome. This system is being used for the first time, we don't have practice and therefore we have nothing to compare it to. We cannot say with absolute certainty about the effectiveness of this innovation. These can be:

Lack of creativity. Information technology does not provide an opportunity to express oneself. Electronic fragments are emotionless in nature. Scientists have proven that creating a color scheme and notes in a notebook helps to remember information better, which in turn promotes creativity.

Weakening of mental abilities. We can observe this phenomenon right now, because to search for the question you are interested in, it is enough to access the Internet and get the necessary information. In the modern world of information technology, a person does not need independent thinking, the global network does everything for him, which in turn leads to a weakening of mental abilities.

Poor socialization. Prospective primary school teachers are less likely to see familiar people in the digital world. He finds himself in another society where he does not know anyone. In an educational institution, he not only gets knowledge, but also communicates with society and friends. Digital technologies significantly weaken the level of socialization of a person, which can negatively affect the development of a person in the future.

Problems of physical development. Staying in front of the computer screen for a long time leads to eye fatigue and then deterioration of vision. Visual fine motor skills suffer first. Keyboard work can change the physiology of the fingers, resulting in changes in the structure of bones, joints and muscles.

Full control. Absolute control belongs to teachers, future elementary school teachers and parents, as a personal case is opened for each of them, detailed information about each family member is collected. If a child gets a bad grade, parents know about it and hide the diary and do not tell about what they got.

There is no bad grade. This is a blow to independence, when problems arise, children try to solve them independently, albeit in the wrong ways.

The task of teachers. After the full implementation of digital technologies in the field of education, experts will be replaced by robots and virtual systems, which in turn will lead to the loss of jobs for teachers.

Thus, summarizing the above, we come to the conclusion that despite the apparent absolute perfection and efficiency of the electronic education system, there are also negative aspects. It is impossible not to highlight the negative impact of digitization on health and physical development. In our opinion, digital technologies should be used in the field of education in such a way that they do not harm anyone. The ideal formula for effective education is a tandem of digital technologies and pedagogues.

REFERENCES

1. Zakirova F.M. Informatika v formirovani medigramotnosti podrastayushego pokoleniya. Respublika ilmiy-amaliy seminari materiallari. (Birinchi kitob) – Namangan, 2015. – B. 125-128.
2. Aripdjanova A.R. Ta’limni axborotlashtirish sharoitida oliy ta’lim muassasalari pedagoglarining kreativ salohiyatini rivojlantirish. Ped. fan. (Rhd) dis. avtoref. – Toshkent, 2017.
3. Abduqodirov A.A., Pardaev A.X. Masofali o’qitish nazariyasi va amaliyoti. “Fan” nashriyoti, Toshkent, 2009. – 145 b.
4. Divanova M.S. O’zbekistonda mediata’limni uzluksiz rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari. // «Uzluksiz ta’lim» ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – № 6. – Toshkent, 2013. 128 b.